

WAYS TO IMPROVE THE PROVISION OF INDIVIDUAL SERVICES IN MODERN CONDITIONS

Musayeva Shoirazimovna

Professor of Samarkand Institute of Economic and Service, Samarkand, Uzbekistan

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Abstract. *This article discusses the principles and approaches to the provision of individual services in the context of overcoming the economic crisis associated with the coronavirus pandemic. The authors explored the possibilities of improving the processes of rendering services and developing the marketing policy of service enterprises.*

Keywords: *services, individual services, retail services, personal services, consumer requirements, service delivery standards.*

Introduction. The socio-economic development of the world economy in modern conditions is characterized by exposure to the influence of many different factors. The processes of globalization have made national economies vulnerable to the dangers and risks observed in other countries and continents. A good example of this is the spread of the coronavirus. In just three months, this disease has changed the economic situation around the world, including the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Over the past three years, Uzbekistan has taken serious steps to overcome the observed negative trends and accelerate the pace of the country's socio-economic development. Fundamental reforms in the field of ensuring the protection of human rights, the inclusion of mechanisms for dialogue with neighboring countries on a variety of issues, the conversion of the national currency, the fight against corruption and the development of market mechanisms have significantly improved macroeconomic indicators. In 2019, the country's gross domestic product reached 511838.1 billion soums, that is, the annual increase is 5.6%. Such sectors as industry, construction, and retail trade have made a great contribution to achieving high performance.

However, the rapid spread of the coronavirus infection forced the government to take drastic measures to mitigate the negative effects of the pandemic. If the first case of the disease was detected on the territory of the country on March 15 this year, then from March 23 a self-isolation regime was introduced in all major cities, and then in other settlements.

Literature analysis. The main document defining the state policy during the pandemic is the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev dated March 19, 2020 "On priority measures to mitigate the negative impact on the economy of the coronavirus pandemic and global crisis phenomena". By this decree, the Republican Commission for Combating the Crisis was formed, which determines the boundaries of self-isolation of the population and the procedure for the activities of business entities during the quarantine period. In addition, a program was adopted to protect business entities from the economic consequences of the self-isolation regime.

In Uzbekistan, service industries and individual entrepreneurs were the first to be affected by the pandemic. In addition to the traditional service industries, all organizations that focus on customer contact were forced to suspend their activities. At the same time, it cannot be expected that the situation after quarantine will return to its original state. Almost all academic economists in Europe and Asia are unanimous in their opinion that one or two years are needed to overcome

the economic consequences of the crisis. Studies by scientists and practitioners indicate a change in the model of consumer behavior of the population. We believe that in the service sector, even this period is not enough, that is, service sector enterprises need to destroy the prevailing stereotypes and use new approaches in the provision of services.

Research methodology. The service sector is one of the most important sectors of the economy of Uzbekistan. According to the statistics authorities, for the first quarter of 2020, the volume of market services provided amounted to 50365.7 billion soums, which is 9.9% more than for the same period in 2019. The highest growth rates were shown by financial services, as well as in the field of communications and informatization. In the structure of services rendered, a large place is occupied by transport, financial, trade services (Table 1).

Table 1

The structure of services rendered by the Republic of Uzbekistan for January-March 2020.

No№	Services list	Volume of rendered services, billion soums	Growth rate, %	Share of services, %
1	Communication and informatization services	2,891.9	117.9	5.74
2	Financial services	10,308.3	136.6	20.47
3	Transport services	13,335.2	103.1	26.47
4	Accommodation and food services	1391.0	98.2	2.76
5	Trade Services	12,335.5	104.4	24.49
6	Services related to real estate	1527.9	101.8	3.03
7	Services in the field of education	2061.4	106.3	4.09
8	Health Services	787.5	116.2	1.56
9	Rental and rental services	1,078.0	105.2	2.14
10	Computer and household goods repair services	805.1	106.0	1.6
eleven	Individual Services	1245.8	103.1	2.47
12	Services in the field of architecture, engineering surveys, technical testing and analysis	921.8	100.8	1.83
13	Other services	1676.3	103.3	3.33
	Total	50,365.7	109.9	100

As a result of the decisions of the Commission for the Organization of Economic Activities during the quarantine period, serious changes have also occurred in the provision of services. First of all, it is necessary to note the destruction of the existing market conditions, that is, in the last month, the volume of traditional types of services has sharply decreased. This is characterized by both sanitary and epidemiological requirements, and a decrease in demand for services, and a change in the consciousness of consumers. Over the past period, Uzbekistan has taken measures to restore the activities of most sectors of the economy, taking into account the current sanitary and epidemiological situation in the country and the world. Consistent relaxation of the quarantine regime, together with measures of state support for entrepreneurship, has significantly reduced

economic losses. It should be noted that negative changes did not affect all types of services, that is, in some types of services, one can even observe a consumer boom. To explore problems from a different angle, it is necessary to expand the features of the classification of services. In the table above, the classification of services is presented according to their content. However, this classification does not reflect the essence and structure of communications between the seller and the buyer of services. This is especially true for individual services, since until today the concepts of individual services and personal services are used as synonyms, but are taken into account in different ways. However, this classification does not reflect the essence and structure of communications between the seller and the buyer of services. This is especially true for individual services, since until today the concepts of individual services and personal services are used as synonyms, but are taken into account in different ways. However, this classification does not reflect the essence and structure of communications between the seller and the buyer of services. This is especially true for individual services, since until today the concepts of individual services and personal services are used as synonyms, but are taken into account in different ways.

Analysis and results. As a result of the research, it was revealed that for an objective assessment of the activities of service sector entities, it is necessary to include an additional classification feature, that is, by the nature of contacts during the provision of services (Table 2). On this basis, services can be grouped into the following groups:

Individual services that require direct contact of the subject with the client in the process of providing services. In this group, we would include such types of services as the transportation of passengers by public transport, retail trade services, household services, hotels and catering establishments, all types of education with compulsory attendance, ceremonial and ritual services, repair and maintenance of equipment for personal use, services with visits to medical institutions, etc.;

Indirect services, that is, services that involve the possibility of their provision using various means of communication without establishing contacts. This group of services includes credit services, payment of payments, government services, transportation of goods, housing and household services, wholesale trade services, services in the field of home economics and agriculture, etc.;

Non-contact services, i.e. services that do not require direct contact to meet the needs of the client. This group includes almost types of communication and informatization services, public utilities, most of the financial services, exchange trading services, distance education services, design and construction services with a contract construction method, etc.

Table 2

Classification of services according to the nature of contacts between the provider and the consumer of services

No№	Services list	The nature of the provision of services
1	Individual Services	The consumer is obliged to personally contact the service provider
2	Indirect services	The consumer is not required to make contact, but must exchange information in the process of providing the service
3	Contactless services	The consumer and the service provider are not bound by the obligations of direct or indirect contact.

Observations of the activities of service enterprises during the period of self-isolation showed that enterprises providing individual services suffered the greatest losses, including in the field of tourism, consumer services, retail and catering. In the current conditions of easing the regime of self-isolation, these enterprises need to develop new principles for organizing activities and ensuring economic well-being. Likewise, consumer preferences will be somewhat different after the end of the self-isolation regime. Therefore, it is necessary to change the approaches to determining the object of service provision. For example, the individuality of a service should not adversely affect its standardity and complexity.

Conclusion and suggestions. An analysis of the content of individual services shows an increased attention of consumers to formal indicators of the quality of a service, that is, to the procedures and process of providing a service. In our opinion, among the priorities in the behavior of consumers of services, the following factors come to the fore:

- ensuring sanitary safety, that is, the attention of the seller of services to the health of the buyer;

- rationality of the service. The need to save money during the period of self-isolation forms consumers' assessment of the service in terms of its necessity. Therefore, the service must meet the buyer's utility criteria;

- the complexity and availability of the service, that is, the effectiveness of the service provided in terms of consumer costs.

In this case, marketing activities are directed not to the consumer, but to the process of providing services. For example, retailers are required to revise their sales service standards to include items such as: information about the number of customers on the sales floor, information about when new products arrive, information about the shortest paths to individual products, the speed of service during the selection of goods, and mutual settlements, organization of delivery of purchases to transport, etc.

Specifications for the provision of individual services by consumer service enterprises also need to be improved. As you know, the process of providing individual household services involves a queue of customers. For normal activities after the coronavirus pandemic, it is necessary to eliminate queues or distribute them in space and time. To do this, in the service process, it is necessary to include the reception of a client at a predetermined time, the organization of recreational areas or separate premises, customer service at home and other forms of service provision.

Thus, the formalization of individual services through the typification and unification of the process of their provision is one of the reserves for the development of the activities of consumer services enterprises.

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